

Outcomes Dissemination and Communication Actions 1

Seascape Belgium

Oonagh McMeel (SSBE), Maria Angel (SSBE), Nathalie Tonné (SSBE), Pieter Torrez (SSBE), Hilary Martínez (SSBE), Joseph Nolan (SSBE), Jula Falvey (SSBE), Bernadette Ní Chonghaile (MI), Frank Armstrong (MI), Anneli Strobel (AWI), Andrea Caburlotto (AWI), Dick Schaap (MARIS)

AQUARIUS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement No 101130915. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

About this document

Title	D7.4, Outcomes Dissemination and Communication Actions 1
Work Package	WP7, Impact: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation and
Lead Partner	Seascope Belgium
Lead Authors (Org)	Oonagh McMeel and Maria Angel
Contributing Author(s)	Nathalie Tonné (SSBE), Pieter Torrez (SSBE), Hilary Martínez (SSBE), Joseph Nolan (SSBE), Jula Falvey (SSBE), Bernadette Ní Chonghaile (MI), Frank Armstrong (MI), Anneli Strobel (AWI), Andrea Caburlotto (AWI), Dick Schaap (MARIS)
Reviewers	Anneli Strobel (AWI)
Due Date	28 February 2026, M24
Submission Date	18/02/2026
Version	1.0

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

AQUARIUS: Aqua Research Infrastructure Services for the health and protection of our unique, oceans, seas and freshwater ecosystems is a Research and Innovation action (RIA) funded by the Horizon Europe Work programme topics addressed: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01-01 - Research infrastructure services to enable R&I addressing main challenges and EU priorities. Start date: 01 March 2024. End date: 29 February 2028.

Funded by
the European Union

AQUARIUS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement No 101130915. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	4
2. Introduction and Background.....	6
2.1. AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Activities: Approach	6
3. Outcomes of the Communication and Dissemination Activities	7
3.1. Phase 1: Awareness Raising and Promotion	7
3.1.1. Website	8
3.1.2. Social Media	10
3.1.3. AQUARIUS press releases.....	12
3.2. Phase 2: Outreach & Engagement	14
3.2.1. Events	15
3.2.2. Communication Toolkits	15
3.2.3. Newsletters and mailing lists.....	16
3.2.4. Pay-Per-Click Campaigns on LinkedIn.....	19
3.2.5. Response to the TA Calls	20
3.2.6. Response to the Training Opportunities	23
3.3. Phase 3: Uptake	26
4. Challenges encountered, opportunities and lessons learned.....	27
5. Conclusion	28
Appendix 1 Communication and Dissemination Activity Log.....	29
Appendix 2 Overview of outreach and engagement campaigns for TA Calls.....	33

1. Executive Summary

This document constitutes the “Outcomes of the AQUARIUS Dissemination and Communication Activities” as Deliverable 7.4 and provides details on the outcomes of the relevant communication and dissemination activities, including the outreach and engagement programme, at the end of the second year of the AQUARIUS project (Month 24).

The AQUARIUS Dissemination and Communication Plans I and II (D7.1) detailed the approach to and implementation of these activities, led by WP7 with involvement of all partners. Dissemination and communication activities were planned and implemented according to three overlapping Phases: Phase 1 - Awareness raising and promotion (Months 1-48); Phase 2: Outreach & Engagement (Months 7-48), and Phase 3 – Uptake (Months 7-48).

Phase 1 “Awareness Raising and Promotion” involved creating a recognisable brand for AQUARIUS and increasing its visibility with target stakeholder groups, in particular the scientific community who would be in a position to avail of the AQUARIUS opportunities. Activities in this Phase successfully established AQUARIUS as a widely recognised new project providing transnational access to research infrastructures. All Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for this phase of the Communication and Dissemination Plan were achieved, and in some cases, the Year 4 targets were exceeded by the end of Year 2. A particular highlight was the steady growth in LinkedIn followers, with 4,008 followers at the time of writing. This is significantly above similar projects of the same duration and is in the range of those for some long-established organisations and entities.

Phase 2, “Outreach and engagement” activities focused on “calls to action” to encourage applications for the two transnational access funding calls (TA Calls) and the training opportunities. These activities have included partners’ participation in events to highlight AQUARIUS and its opportunities through oral and poster presentations, booth and brokerage event organisation, newsletters and targeted email campaigns, and communication support through press releases, videos, blogs, social media calls to action, and the website.

The KPIs for this Phase have been achieved or are in line to be achieved by project end. To date, activities in this Phase have resulted in 61 applications to both the TA Calls and 119 applications to the training opportunities. These represent an internationally diverse applicant profile, with principal investigators from 10 countries and group members from 27 countries in response to Call 1, while for Call 2, principal investigators came from 17 different countries with team members from 24 countries. While the majority of applications came from those in research or academic backgrounds, applications were also received from public- and private-sector organisations, as well as not-for-profit entities.

Phase 3 of the Dissemination and Communication Plan concerns the dissemination and uptake of AQUARIUS outputs. To date, this Phase has focused on sharing AQUARIUS deliverables and training resources via the project website, YouTube channel, via the Zenodo community page and through social media as they become available. Informative deliverables and outputs of relevance to wider stakeholders are promoted more widely through social media, at events and through dedicated news items to encourage uptake, e.g. the AQUARIUS Data Management Plan. Relevant KPIs for the current period associated to Phase 3 have been achieved.

The terminology around transnational access, research infrastructures, and Mission Ocean and Waters is complex and niche. Efforts were made to simplify this, particularly in communicating TA Call 2, making opportunities clear to wider stakeholders. Simplified messaging and more targeted outreach for the second Call resulted in increased

participation from industry and civil society, while the scientific and academic communities remained the primary applicants due to the relevance of the opportunity to their work and their familiarity with the terminology and application processes. Promotion of training opportunities proved particularly effective in rapidly increasing the visibility of AQUARIUS and expanding stakeholder engagement. Partner support in communication was a key success factor, as was direct messaging to contacts. Providing consortium members and externals with ready-to-use communication materials ensured message consistency and reduced barriers to participation.

The outcomes of the AQUARIUS communication and dissemination activities in the current period have been successful in raising the visibility of AQUARIUS and in achieving strong engagement, resulting in good responses to the TA Calls and training opportunities. In the absence of further Calls for transnational access, subsequent communication and dissemination activities will focus on the training opportunities, disseminating and encouraging uptake of AQUARIUS outputs, and in raising the visibility of the extent and strategic value of Europe's research infrastructure landscape for wider society.

2. Introduction and Background

This document constitutes the “Outcomes of the AQUARIUS Dissemination and Communication Activities” as Deliverable 7.4 and provides details on the outcomes of the relevant communication and dissemination activities, including the outreach and engagement programme at the end of the second year of the AQUARIUS project (Month 24). This document will be updated to a second version by the end of the project.

The AQUARIUS Dissemination and Communication Plans I and II (D7.1) detailed the approach to and implementation of these activities, led by WP7 with involvement of all partners.

2.1. AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Activities: Approach

The overall aim of the AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Strategy (as detailed in D7.1) is to maximise the impact of the project and has the following objectives:

1. To raise awareness of AQUARIUS, its activities and the value of this public investment amongst diverse stakeholders, including wider society;
2. To maximise engagement of target stakeholder groups throughout the project and beyond, by encouraging applications to the TA Calls and training opportunities;
3. To maximise exploitation of AQUARIUS results and those of the selected projects towards generating long-term impact for the project;
4. To create a legacy for AQUARIUS.

These objectives are being implemented through a phased approach. Three overlapping communication and dissemination phases were identified, each with a distinct purpose and related Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), as follows:

Phase 1: Awareness Raising and Promotion (Months 1-48)

Purpose: To raise awareness and visibility with all stakeholder groups.

While this phase runs throughout the entire project, its main purpose in the first two years was to raise awareness and visibility of AQUARIUS as a new project in the “Transnational access to research infrastructures” landscape, highlighting the unique nature of AQUARIUS in providing access to such a diversity of both marine and freshwater research infrastructures. As such, this phase involved creating a recognisable brand for AQUARIUS and continued to highlight relevant news, activities, outputs, training materials, and the successful TA Projects, as well as activities in the broader landscape in which AQUARIUS operates.

Phase 2: Outreach & Engagement (Months 7-48)

Purpose: To promote active engagement with AQUARIUS opportunities.

This phase focuses on targeting stakeholders with specific ‘calls to action’ to promote their engagement with AQUARIUS activities. A significant focus of this phase in the first two years of the AQUARIUS project was to solicit applications to the TA Calls via two dedicated outreach and engagement campaigns (one for each Call). This phase also promotes applications to AQUARIUS training opportunities for early-career researchers (ECRs) and technicians and encourages registration for other AQUARIUS events and activities (e.g., brokerage events, webinars). While the main thrust of this activity unfolded from month seven to the close of the second TA Call (October 2025), ECR training opportunities and other activities will run throughout the project.

Phase 3: Uptake (Months 7-48)

Purpose: To disseminate and promote uptake of project key exploitable results (KER) and outputs (deliverables, factsheets, infographics, training webinars, data flows and

products), both from AQUARIUS itself and from the successful TA Projects as a first step towards their exploitation (as detailed in D7.2, "Exploitation Plan Outline").

In the first two years of the project, activities in this phase have focused on disseminating key project deliverables and training resources.

The following section details the outcomes of the communication and dissemination activities relevant to each of these phases.

3. Outcomes of the Communication and Dissemination Activities

3.1. Phase 1: Awareness Raising and Promotion

AQUARIUS builds on and brings together distributed and established European research infrastructures (EMBRC, EMSO-ERIC & EUFAR), as well as previous and existing projects and initiatives (JERICO, Eurofleets+). However, "AQUARIUS" was a new name in the landscape of research infrastructure projects so creating brand recognition for the project was a priority.

A first step existed in creating a recognisable visual identity for AQUARIUS. This was achieved with a strong logo, shared branding guidelines and templates for all partners, and consistent branding across all materials, content and channels. This was all laid out in the AQUARIUS Dissemination and Communication Plans I & II, along with key messages that all partners could use to explain AQUARIUS, its objectives, and what it offered to the relevant stakeholder groups.

AQUARIUS introductory slide decks, brochures, infographic, poster, pull-up banners and other outreach materials were developed and made available to partners (Figure 1). The AQUARIUS website and social media channels were established to initially introduce the project, its objectives and outputs.

Figure 1 AQUARIUS-branded materials and tools to support brand recognition

As we approach the two-year mark for AQUARIUS, it is now a well-recognised entity in the European research infrastructure landscape. As the European Commission launched its [Ocean Pact](#) (adopted on June 5th, 2025), AQUARIUS was one of a number of projects

highlighted in a related article from the European Research Executive Agency demonstrating how EU-backed research contributes to protecting & restoring our oceans¹. All Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for Phase 1 of the Communication and Dissemination Plan were achieved, and in some cases, the Year 4 targets were exceeded by the end of Year 2, as detailed in Table 1, below.

Table 1 Key Performance Indicators for Phase 1 "Awareness & Promotion"

Phase 1 Awareness & Promotion	KPIs	
	Target (month 48)	Status (month 24)
Raise awareness of AQUARIUS and its activities.	1 toolkit	1 general toolkit, 1 toolkit on the brokerage event, 2 promotional toolkits to promote TA Funding Calls
	2 roll -up banners	4 roll-ups
	+3000 visits to the AQUARIUS project website	113,106 page views; 46,193 sessions ² ; 78,432 user engagement ³ ; 28,950 total users; average engagement time per user 1min 48sec
	+500 followers (Social media)	4,008 LinkedIn followers, 125 X followers, 52 Instagram followers
	10 newsletters	5 newsletters, 3 newsflashes
	+2000 brochures distributed	760+ brochures distributed (online + physical); 300 flyers distributed; 300+ postcards distributed
	+500 downloads infographics & factsheets	164 downloads from the website, but viewed widely on LinkedIn (Impressions ⁴ 2,581, clicks 183)
	+500 views for 4 videos	886 (YouTube); 20,920 (LinkedIn)
	+5000 clicks in Pay Per Click campaigns	2,008 clicks and 187,376 impressions resulting from PPC campaigns

3.1.1. Website

The AQUARIUS website was developed as an engaging, user-friendly hub for all project information. It was initially launched for the project kick-off meeting in April 2024 with basic information but was developed by Month 6 to host the curated and interactive Research Infrastructure Catalogue (with WPs 2 & 4), and subsequently the Training Hub and Opportunities pages (with WP5), as well as all the detailed information on the two TA Calls (with WP3) including a link to the Transnational Access Platform (TAP). It now also provides an overview page for the projects funded under TA Call 1, as well as individual pages for each project. These are, in turn, linked to the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD) developed in WP6.

¹ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/news/blueprint-blue-waters-eu-backed-research-protecting-restoring-our-oceans-2025-06-04_en

² Definition session: A session is a single visit to a website, which can include one or more actions. A page view is one instance of a page being loaded or viewed.

³ Definition user engagement: Measure of how actively users interact with a website.

⁴ Definition impression: Count of how many times content is shown to users.

Over the first two years of the project, the AQUARIUS website has attracted more than 26K unique users, generating more than 46K sessions, with an average of 2 sessions per user.

As shown in Figure 2 below, the main peaks in website activity correspond to periods of intensified communication linked to key project events, including the launch of the RI Catalogue, training opportunities and the launch of the two TA Calls.

Figure 2 Google Analytics graph showing user activity on the AQUARIUS website from its launch in April 2024 to January 2026.

Figure 3 Google Analytics graph showing page views on the AQUARIUS website from its launch in April 2024 to January 2026.

3.1.2. Social Media

LinkedIn remains the primary social media channel for AQUARIUS while engagement with X was gradually discontinued in late 2024/early 2025. LinkedIn has been extremely successful for AQUARIUS, with over 4,100 followers as of writing. This is significantly above similar projects of approximately the same duration (AQUA-Serv 1,800; POLARIN 1,300) and is in the range of, or higher than, those for long-established organisations and entities, e.g., European Marine Board = 3,400 followers, EuroGOOS = 2,600 followers, EMODnet = 4,000 followers and JPI Oceans 5,300 followers.

While the TA Calls generated significant interest, the training opportunities for early-career scientists elicited the highest engagement, resulting in notable increases in followers for those posts. Figure 4, below, shows LinkedIn follower metrics, specifically daily new followers over the last year. Figure 5 relates the peaks in new followers to specific AQUARIUS activities, such as new training opportunities or the launch of the 2nd TA Call.

Figure 4 LinkedIn follower metrics from January 2025 to January 2026 showing number of new followers. The peaks can be associated to particular AQUARIUS activities, such as the launch of new training opportunities, or the launch of the second TA Call. (See Figure 5 below)

Figure 5 LinkedIn follower growth over the project lifetime (March 2024 to January 2026). The graph shows a steady growth and periods with rapid growth (e.g. February 2025 AQUARIUS General Assembly in Helsinki; and May 2025 AQUARIUS at EGU).

6 May 2025 → 102 new followers

13 June 2025 → 34 new followers

2 September → 39 new followers

3 October → 57 new followers

3 December → 21 new followers

19 December → 19 new followers

Figure 6 A series of six LinkedIn posts showing high engagement and which resulted in peaks in new followers, as indicated in Figure 5, above.

3.1.3. AQUARIUS press releases

A press release was created and shared with all partners in advance of each TA Call. These were picked up and published by several online industry and research platforms, including from Ireland, the UK, Sweden and Australia (Figure 7 and Tables 2 and 3, below).

Figure 7 A series of online news and trade platforms that picked up on the AQUARIUS press release.

Table 2 Overview of organisations and news sites that advertised AQUARIUS Funding Call 1

Outlet/Website	URL
Marine Ireland Industry Network	https://marine-ireland.ie/node/1522
Fish Focus, UK Online Trade Magazine	https://fishfocus.co.uk/aquarius-project-launches-first-call/
NANO POGO Alumni Network (Global Ocean Alumni Network)	https://nf-pogo-alumni.org/22112024-11/
Technology Centre Prague (both calls highlighted in one article)	https://www.horizontevropa.cz/en/news/yiifnews/2912
Silicon Republic (Science and tech online newsite, Ireland)	https://www.siliconrepublic.com/innovation/aquarius-funding-call-marine-research
Baird Maritime (Maritime website, Australia)	https://www.bairdmaritime.com/work-boat-world/research-environment-training/marine-institute-of-ireland-launches-funding-round-to-support-research-activities
The Fishing Daily (Irish Fishing Industry news site)	https://thefishingdaily.com/irish-fishing-industry-news/aquarius-project-launches-first-call-in-funding-to-support-research/
AFLOAT - Irelands Sailing, Boating and Maritime Magazine	https://afloat.ie/marine-environment/marine-science/item/65354-marine-institute-s-aquarius-project-launches-first-call-for-8-1m-to-support-marine-and-freshwater-research
Doors Black Sea Website, Mission Ocean CSA	https://www.doorsblacksea.eu/post/770142503275020288/first-aquarius-transnational-funding-call-open
Observatorio Tecnológico CTN (Spanish maritime tech blog)	https://observatorio.ctnaval.com/blog/2024/12/03/convocatorias-aquarius
Aclima (Basque Environment Cluster)	https://aclima.eus/en/noticia/convocatoria-eu-mision-ocean-and-waters-area-based-lighthouses-in-major-sea-river-basins-atlantic-arctic-mediterranean-sea-baltic-north-sea-and-danube-black-sea/
Technological Platform for the Protection of the Coast and the Marine Environment (Spain)	https://ptprotecma.es/convocatoria/eu-research-infrastructure-project-aquarius-launches-tna-funding/

Table 3 Overview of organisations and news sites that advertised AQUARIUS Funding Call 2

Outlet/Website	URL
West Med Initiative (Western Mediterranean Blue Economy initiative)	https://westmed-initiative.ec.europa.eu/second-aquarius-funding-call-marine-and-freshwater-infrastructure-access-deadline-28-october-2025/
Technology Centre Prague	https://www.horizontevropa.cz/en/news/yiifnews/3570/aquarius---marine-and-freshwater-infrastructure...
EurOcean (European centre for information in marine science and technology)	https://eurocean.org/np4/1935.html
EU Blue Economy Observatory	https://blue-economy-observatory.ec.europa.eu/news/aquarius-launch-call-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-2030-2025-06-03_en
UN Decade Coordination Office for Ocean Data Sharing	https://oceandatasharing-dco.org/news/funding-call-aquarius-marine-and-freshwater-infrastructure-access/
Fish Focus, UK Online Trade Magazine	https://fishfocus.co.uk/aquarius-project-launches-second-e4-million-funding-call/
Marine Ireland Industry Network	https://marine-ireland.ie/node/1649
Atlantic Strategy Europe	https://atlantic-maritime-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/funding/calls/second-aquarius-funding-call-marine-and-freshwater-infrastructure-access
Pole Mer Bretagne Atlantique (French maritime cluster)	https://www.pole-mer-bretagne-atlantique.com/opportunitites-app-ami/appel-projet-aquarius
Innovation Europe, Italy	https://www.europainnovazione.com/aperto-il-bando-aquarius-per-laccesso-a-infrastrutture-marine-e-dacqua-dolce/
NANO POGO Alumni Network (Global Ocean Alumni Network)	https://nf-pogo-alumni.org/09092025-3/

3.2. Phase 2: Outreach & Engagement

In the first two years of the project, outreach and engagement activities focused on “calls to action” to encourage applications for the two TA Calls and the training opportunities. These activities have included partners’ participation in events to highlight AQUARIUS and its opportunities through oral and poster presentations, booth and brokerage event organisation, newsletters and targeted email campaigns, and communication support through press releases, videos, blogs, social media calls to action, and the website.

The KPIs for this Phase are detailed in Table 4. The activities to date in this Phase have resulted in 61 applications to the TA calls and 119 applications to the training opportunities. Further detail is provided in the sections below on the relevant activities and their outcomes.

Table 4 Key performance indicators for Phase 2, "Outreach and Engagement"

Phase 2	KPIs	
	Target (month 48)	Status (month 24)
Outreach & Engagement	3000 researchers targeted	3,000+ researchers targeted (AQUARIUS highlighted at 53 events in 18 countries (Annex 1), email campaign to Research networks including JPIOceans, European Marine Board, EurOcean, EuroGOOS, EMODnet, partners networks and Mission Ocean projects.
	500+ citizen science groups contacted	300+ citizen science groups contacted (email campaign to citizen science organisations, LinkedIn)
	3+ citizen science groups directly engaged in TA projects	3+ organisations that engage in citizen science activities directly engaged in TA projects (for further details on this KPI, see section 3.2.5)
	500+ industry stakeholders targeted	300+ industry stakeholders targeted (email campaign to maritime clusters, LinkedIn)
	+50 applications	19 applications to TA Call 1 42 applications to TA Call 2 117 applications to training opportunities
	5+ Mission actions informed about AQUARIUS tools and/or services	50+ Mission Actions informed (email to Mission CSAs, Poster at Mission Forum, LinkedIn post reposted by Mission LinkedIn account)
	1000 visits to the training repository	832 visits to Training Hub page; 2,998 visits to Training Opportunities page; 2,089 visits to Training landing page

3.2.1. Events

In the first two years of AQUARIUS, partners participated in 53 events across 18 countries. (Annex 1). As part of the dedicated outreach and engagement activities for the launch of the first TA Call, a series of sea-basin brokerage events were organised, led by the project Coordinator Marine Institute. These included booths at the ICES Annual Science Meeting (Reading, UK), the MonGOOS General Assembly (Malaga, Spain), the MarBlue Conference (Constanta, Romania). A final online brokerage event was organised as a Webinar.

To promote the launch of TA Call 2, booths were organised at the EGU General Assembly and the All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance Platform, and an online Webinar was again arranged to share all the Call-specific details. In addition to the dedicated booths, partners promoted the Calls through oral and poster presentations and disseminated flyers at a range of events.

Figure 8 An overview of events where AQUARIUS was promoted by partners during the current period

3.2.2. Communication Toolkits

In advance of both TA Calls, dedicated communication toolkits were developed and shared with all partners to support consistent, partner-wide outreach activities. These included social media posts, engaging graphics, press releases, email templates that could be forwarded and/or adapted, newsletters, website banners, and digital flyers. In some instances, these were also shared with external networks and contacts when they were approached to help promote the Calls.

When something is easy to do, people are significantly more likely to do it. This principle underpinned the success of the AQUARIUS communication toolkits. By providing partners with clear, effective messaging and ready-to-use materials, the effort and uncertainty often associated with project communication was removed, leading to broader reach, more consistent messaging, and stronger community engagement across the consortium.

The purpose of the toolkits was to minimise the effort required for partners or their communication departments to share information through their networks. Feedback from the partners on the quality and usefulness of these Toolkits was very positive. The effectiveness of the communication toolkits was evident in the social media pages and websites of AQUARIUS partners, where the posts and messaging, as well as branded

graphics, were used to promote the TA Calls and other AQUARIUS opportunities (Figure 9). An example of the Toolkit is available from the AQUARIUS website (for the second Call).

Marine Institute Website

EMSO-ERIC Website

Vito Remote Sensing Website

Istituto Hidrografico Portugal Website

Figure 9 A selection of screenshots from Partners' websites where they used the materials in the Communication Toolkit to highlight Call 2.

3.2.3. Newsletters and mailing lists

AQUARIUS issues a quarterly digital newsletter to which stakeholders can subscribe via the AQUARIUS website (the subscription link is also promoted via social media). Subscriptions have grown gradually throughout the project (Figure 8 Newsletter Dashboard). Subscribers are invited to indicate their sea-basin and sector on subscription, although this is not a mandatory request. Clearly, the highest number of subscribers is from the research/academia domain (200), which is not surprising given the relevance of AQUARIUS and its opportunities to this community. Although all sea-basins are represented, the majority of subscribers identify their sea basin as "Mediterranean" (158) or "Atlantic". To mark the opening of both Calls, a dedicated "newsflash" was released. These proved useful for all partners to forward to their networks and mailing lists. In addition to sending these to registered subscribers, WP7 partners forwarded them to more than 40 multipliers and networks identified in the target stakeholder groups in the Communication & Dissemination Plan. This resulted in the AQUARIUS Calls being promoted through the newsletters and/or social media accounts of, amongst others, the Mission Ocean Communications group, Blue Cluster, ENVRI, JPI Oceans, European Marine Board, EurOcean, EMODnet and the UN Decade Ocean Data Sharing Decade Coordination Office. Other organisations responded to say that they would circulate the information through their own contacts.

Figure 10 Screenshots of the AQUARIUS newsletter dashboard showing, above, the number of subscribers and their identified sea basin, and below, their identified sector.

European Marine Board Newsletter “EMB Message to the Board - 5 September 2025”

**AQUARIUS Funding Call:
Marine and Freshwater Infrastructure Access**

The Horizon Europe **AQUARIUS** project has launched the second of two funding calls to support marine and freshwater research and innovation projects to access a diverse array of world-class research infrastructure services.

Open for applications from
2 September 2025 – 28 October 2025

The objective of this call is to advance marine and freshwater research and innovation, promote transnational scientific collaboration, and raise awareness of Europe’s array of top-class research infrastructures.

More details about this call [here](#). Deadline to submit is 28 October 2025.

EuroOcean Website

AQUARIUS
Funding Call
Marine and
Freshwater Infrastructure Access

Open for applications from
2 September 2025 – 28 October 2025

Second AQUARIUS Funding Call Opens
September 2

The second AQUARIUS Transnational Access Funding Call will open on 2 September 2025, offering researchers, industry, and other science groups free access to world-class marine and freshwater research infrastructures. Nothing on feedback from the first call: the round includes updated eligibility criteria.

- Single applicants are now eligible.
- Only single user groups (i.e. users from different organisations) need to include a contract form in their bid.

UN Ocean Data Sharing Decade Coordination Office Website

Ocean Data Sharing

Funding Call AQUARIUS – Marine and Freshwater Infrastructure Access

Open for applications from
2 September 2025 – 28 October 2025

Following the success of the first Transnational Access Funding Call, we are pleased to announce the second round of the call.

The second round of the call is open to a wider range of researchers and researchers from outside Europe. This round is expected to support marine and freshwater research and innovation projects to access a diverse array of world-class research infrastructure services.

Single users are now eligible to submit an application to the call. The call includes updated eligibility criteria.

Open from **September 2nd until September 28th 2025**. The funding will support projects to access world-class marine and freshwater research infrastructures. Nothing on feedback from the first call: the round includes updated eligibility criteria.

EMODnet Newsletter

AQUARIUS launches Funding Call for access to Marine and Freshwater Research Infrastructures, fostering publication through EMODnet

The Horizon Europe project AQUARIUS is launching a funding call on 2 September 2025 for transnational access to a portfolio of marine and freshwater research infrastructures, in support of the EU Mission Ocean and Waters. The funded projects will be guided to implement a dedicated data management approach, ensuring collected data and metadata will be managed in line with the FAIR principles. The data will be ingested into EMODnet, which is in turn feeding into the European Digital Twin data lake (EU-DTO). Find out more: <https://www.aquaserv-ri.eu/transnational-access-call/>

Open for applications from
2 September 2025 – 28 October 2025

What to do next?

1. Visit our website for all the Call information.
2. From 2 September 2025 register on the AQUARIUS Transnational Access Platform (TAP) and activate your account.
3. Check our Research Infrastructure Catalogue.
4. Contact the operators to find out whether your proposal can be implemented as planned.
5. Fill in the application form in the TAP.
6. Review and submit your application.

Figure 11 Screenshots showing where AQUARIUS was promoted by third-party organisations who were contacted by WP7 and asked to share the information on the Calls.

Blue Cluster Newsletter

Marine Ireland Industry Network

EU Blue Economy Observatory

FishFocus News site

Figure 12 Selection of blue economy organisations or initiatives that promoted the second AQUARIUS TA Call

3.2.4. Pay-Per-Click Campaigns on LinkedIn

On LinkedIn, AQUARIUS maintains consistently high organic visibility, averaging approximately 15,000 organic impressions per month. While organic performance remains strong, Pay Per Click (PPC) campaigns have proven effective for reaching large audiences within short timeframes. Sponsored campaigns were therefore used during both TA Calls.

The first PPC campaign, launched in January 2025, was particularly successful and contributed significantly to the project's overall impression growth during the year. In total, six LinkedIn PPC campaigns were implemented to promote the Calls and AQUARIUS training opportunities. Collectively, these campaigns generated more than 2,000 clicks and visits to the project website. In addition, AQUARIUS content achieved over 187,376 sponsored impressions on LinkedIn (48% of the total impressions for 2025), increasing the project's visibility and reinforcing its credibility among key target audiences.

Building on this strong performance, paid campaigns will continue to be used strategically to further raise the AQUARIUS profile and ensure that information on the project's objectives, opportunities, and results reaches the widest possible audience.

Figure 13 Screenshot of LinkedIn analytics from January 2025 to January 2026. The graph shows impressions, defined as the number of times AQUARIUS content was displayed on users' screens. The sharp increase between January and March 2025 reflects the impressions linked to training opportunities.

3.2.5. Response to the TA Calls

The first of two TA Calls, the "Regional Lighthouse Access Call", closed on January 20th, 2025. A total of 19 project proposals were submitted by the deadline. These proposals spanned all Mission Lighthouse Areas, with principal investigators from 10 countries, and teams from 27 countries (Table 5) and five scientific disciplines⁵, applying for a range of research infrastructure types and selecting 26 of the 57 research infrastructures. The term "user group" refers to the project partners or "teams" in the proposals. The vast majority of the user groups (i.e. the project partners or "teams" who submitted the proposals) were from academia or public sector research institutes (Figure 14).

There was a much greater response to the second TA Call with 42 applications led by principal investigators from 17 countries, and teams spanning 24 countries (Table 5) and 11 disciplines. There was also a notable increase in users from other sectors than research/academia (private, private non-profit and "other", Figure 14). This may reflect the increase in the variety of the disciplines of the submitted proposals (Table 6).

This also reflects a more targeted approach to the blue economy and citizen science organisations in the second campaign, through social media and emails to maritime clusters. Two targeted social media posts were developed to increase applications for access to Research Infrastructures in the Mediterranean and the Baltic and North Sea regions, since these were less represented in the successful projects following Call 1. In parallel, Research Infrastructure categories that had been underrepresented in the first

⁵Applicants must identify their scientific disciplines according to those indicated in the AQUARIUS TA Platform

Call were given greater visibility, including targeted posts focusing on Mobile Marine Observation Platforms (Figure 15).

Of the funded projects from Call 1, seven of the organisations engaged in the projects engage in citizen science activities (as specified on their websites), in terms of organisation type, three of these identified as "other" and four as "public research institutes", of the latter one is a foundation and two are museums. While the proposals to Call 2 are still under evaluation, of the proposals received, they include six organisations identified as "other", "private" or "Private non Profit Research Association" who engage in citizen science activities (as specified on their websites).

Table 5 Table showing the number of nationalities of the principal investigators and user group (team) members in response to Call 1 and Call 2

Principal Investigators Countries				User Group Member Countries			
Call 1		Call 2		Call 1		Call 2	
Country	No.	Country	No.	Country	No.	Country	No.
Belgium	3	Spain	8	Greenland	7	Germany	13
	1	Portugal	8	United Kingdom	24	Spain	8
Cyprus	1	Sweden	5	Ireland	2	Portugal	6
Germany	1	Italy	4	Norway	7	Italy	6
Denmark	1	Norway	4	Faroe Islands	5	United Kingdom	6
Great Britain	5	United Kingdom	4	Iceland	3	France	4
Greenland	1	Germany	3	Germany	12	Norway	4
Italy	2	France	2	Netherlands	4	Estonia	3
Netherlands	1	Estonia	2	Poland	1	Sweden	3
Poland	1	Austria	1	Portugal	5	Greece	3
Romania	1	Latvia	1	Denmark	15	Belgium	3
		Czech Republic	1	Sweden	3	Denmark	3
		Poland	1	Romania	6	Czech Republic	2
		Belgium	1	Bulgaria	6	Ireland	2
		Ireland	1	Turkey	3	Turkey	2
		Turkey	1	France	6	Romania	2
		Romania	1	Belgium	21	Latvia	2
				Estonia	4	United States	2
				Italy	39	Brazil	1
				Spain	6	Finland	1
				Canada	1	Lithuania	1
				Slovenia	2	Switzerland	1
				Greece	1	Cape Verde	1
				United States	5	Morocco	1
				Cyprus	4		
				Croatia	2		

Figure 14 Chart showing the user organisation type as identified in the proposals submitted to both Calls.

Table 6 Scientific disciplines of the submitted proposals to both Calls

Call 1		Call 2	
Topic	Number	Topic	Number
Marine science/Oceanography	11	Marine science / Oceanography	19
Ecosystems & Biodiversity	3	Ecosystems & Biodiversity	6
Earth Sciences	2	Earth Sciences	1
Earth Sciences & Environment: Global change & Climate observation	1	Water sciences / Hydrology	2
Information & Communication technologies: Knowledge & interface technologies	1	Global change & Climate observation	2
		Environment	1
		Life Sciences & Biotech	2
		Molecular and cellular biology	1
		Agriculture & Fisheries	1
		Engineering & Technology	1
		Sustainable energy systems	1

Figure 15 A selection of the targeted geographic, sectoral or research infrastructure-focused LinkedIn posts issued in TA Call 2.

3.2.6. Response to the Training Opportunities

There was an international response to all the training opportunities, reflecting the international reach of AQUARIUS communications. Table 7 and Figures 16-18 below show the overall number of applications to each of the training opportunities (to date) and the number of applications per country. Currently, the most applications have been received for the Marine and Freshwater Internships; however, this reflects the fact that it is an open (ongoing) call and also covers a diversity of disciplines. The first edition of the PLOCAN glider school received 30 applications over the six-month period from January to June 2025, while the INFOMAR Seabed Mapping Training programme was the most popular, receiving 40 applications over the two-month period from 6 May 2025 to 13 June 2025.

Table 7 Details on the number of applications and the number of different nationalities of the applicants to the training opportunities offered to date.

Training Opportunity	Period Open	Number of Applicants	Number of applicant nationalities
Marine & Freshwater Internships	October 2024 to current	47	24
PLOCAN Glider School	January 2024 to June 2024 (1 st edition)	30	20
INFOMAR Seabed Mapping programme	May to June 13 2025	40	25

Figure 16 Graph showing the number of nationalities of applicants to the Marine and Freshwater Internships training opportunity.

Figure 17 Graph showing the number of nationalities of applicants to the PLOCAN glider school training opportunity

Figure 18 Graph showing the number of nationalities of applicants to the Seabed Mapping Training programme

3.3. Phase 3: Uptake

Phase 3 of the Dissemination and Communication Plan concerns the dissemination and uptake of AQUARIUS outputs. To date, this Phase has focused on sharing AQUARIUS deliverables and training resources via the project website, YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@AQUARIUS-RI-q5w>), via the Zenodo community page and through social media as they become available. Informative deliverables and outputs of relevance to wider stakeholders are promoted more widely through social media, at events and through dedicated news items to encourage uptake, e.g. the AQUARIUS Data Management Plan. Relevant KPIs for the current period associated to Phase 3 have been achieved (Table 8).

As the outputs (KER) from the funded projects become available, these will also be promoted by AQUARIUS according to the individual exploitation plans that are under development in Task 7.4. One of the most important outputs of the funded projects is expected to be data, which will flow directly to the relevant data centres, according to the AQUARIUS Data Management Plan. These can be tracked via the AQUARIUS Data Flow Dashboard, accessible through the AQUARIUS website.

As further AQUARIUS outputs become available as the project progresses, such as the AQUARIUS policy brief, these will be widely shared with relevant stakeholders to maximise their impact.

Table 8 Key Performance Indicators for Phase 3, "Uptake"

Phase 3	KPIs	
	Target Month 48	Month 24
Uptake (M7-M48)	+200 Downloads of AQUARIUS outputs	625 downloads of AQUARIUS outputs from Zenodo
	+200 views of AQUARIUS Training Webinars	Webinar TA Call How to apply: 238 views Webinar TA Call 2: 23 views Webinar use TAP: 115 views Webinar Fair data principles: 46 views Webinar data management: 59 views Total: 458 views
	+300 downloads of AQUARIUS policy brief	Not applicable at Month 24
	70+ participants informed of AQUARIUS vision and recommendations towards marine and freshwater RIs of the future	Not applicable at Month 24

4. Challenges encountered, opportunities and lessons learned

The name AQUARIUS is an acronym for the full project title. From a communication perspective, it created some difficulties in the early stages as it is a widely known and used term for other reasons. The term AQUARIUS-RI was adopted for the website and social media URLs to overcome this. Future projects that build on AQUARIUS could adopt this acronym, as it is easier for **brand recognition** and search engine optimisation is improved when the project's name is a unique acronym or more clearly links to the subject area, e.g., "EuroFleets".

TA Call 1 was launched relatively early in the AQUARIUS project's lifecycle, in month 9 (November 2023). This was necessary to allow time for subsequent calls to be issued and for the implementation of the funded TA projects within the project's four-year lifespan. The slightly lower response to Call 1 may be due to ongoing brand recognition growth, the associated lower numbers of subscribers to social media and the newsletters during the project's first year, as well as the Call opening period overlapping with Christmas holidays.

The **terminology** around transnational access and research infrastructures can be quite niche and complex. The term "transnational access" is understood by those in the community who have been involved in previous transnational access projects or who provide access to research infrastructures. Equally, the term "research infrastructures" can mean different things to different communities. It is less obvious to external stakeholders, particularly those outside the research community (industry, civil society), what is on offer or how to apply. Efforts were made across all communications (website, social media, emails, and newsletters, as well as in communication assets) to simplify messaging and clarify terminology as much as possible. This also extends to the terminology associated with the Mission Ocean and Waters, particularly related to the "Lighthouse Areas". For this reason, while Call 1 was named the "Regional Lighthouse Access Call", the second Call was simplified to "AQUARIUS Funding Call: Marine and Freshwater Infrastructure Access".

This approach to **simplify messaging**, together with a greater communication effort to target stakeholders from civil society and industry for the second Call, resulted in more individuals from these sectors making up the teams responding to the second Call. Given that the project is focused on delivering new scientific knowledge and innovation, and that the use and interpretation of data collected from research infrastructures require specialist scientific knowledge, it is understandable that the scientific community from research and academic backgrounds is the primary target and respondent to the Calls. The application process terminology and requirements are also more familiar to applicants from these communities. **Staying on message** in social media is also important to retain followers. Followers know that they will get AQUARIUS-relevant information only.

The **promotion of training opportunities** proved to be a highly effective mechanism for rapidly growing AQUARIUS's stakeholder community, particularly among early-career scientists, PhD and MSc students, and their professors, universities and research organisations, as well as wider networks and projects who themselves know that highlighting training opportunities increases engagement. Training activities consistently generated high levels of engagement across communication channels, helping to position AQUARIUS as a known and respected initiative within the research infrastructure community. For research infrastructure access projects with longer lifecycles, this represents a particularly strong strategy: training provides an accessible entry point for new audiences to become familiar with the project's objectives, services, and available Research Infrastructures. As these early-career researchers progress professionally, they are more likely to return to the project as applicants for TA Calls through their own research projects. Including training opportunities for early-career scientists, with

associated costs, in future projects (not only in the transnational access domain) is an excellent way to increase the project's visibility, strengthen European research capacity, and maximise the impact of research and innovation funding programmes.

Direct one-to-one contact via conversations with or emails to collaborators, colleagues or known contacts in networks is very effective both to spread the word, but also in soliciting responses to the Calls. Having the opportunity to share information at other projects' general assembly meetings is also useful.

Communication and outreach support from partners, particularly when a partner has a strong communications department, is highly effective in increasing visibility and engagement at national level. Consortium partners, including established Research Infrastructures, were effective in disseminating information about the project and its opportunities, especially when provided with clear, practical communication support. WP7 eliminated known barriers to partner engagement by developing "**Communication Toolkits**" containing ready-to-use social media posts, adaptable visuals and banners for partner websites, short videos, and pre-written email content that could be shared directly with existing networks. This approach ensured message consistency while minimising the time and effort required from partners. The strong level of partner participation in the communication campaigns demonstrates that when consortium members are equipped with clear, high-quality, and easily deployable materials, they are both willing and proactive in communicating about the project and its opportunities. Leveraging partners networks, including their participation to other projects through promotion of AQUARIUS at other project general assemblies, e.g. Ocean ICU, or CS-MACH1 also proved a useful way to directly contact scientists and relevant stakeholders.

5. Conclusion

The outcomes of the AQUARIUS communication and dissemination activities in the current period have been successful in raising the visibility of AQUARIUS and in achieving strong engagement with the AQUARIUS opportunities resulting in applications to the TA Calls and Training Opportunities. As there will be no further Calls for transnational access, communication and dissemination activities in the remainder of the project will focus on the training opportunities, disseminating and encouraging uptake of AQUARIUS outputs and in raising the visibility of the extent and strategic value of Europe's research infrastructure landscape for wider society.

Appendix 1 Communication and Dissemination Activity Log

Table 9 AQUARIUS partners' Communication and Dissemination Activity Log (January 2026)

Dissemination Activity name	Date	Type of Dissemination Activity	Who? Target audience reach	Audience Size	Location (city, country)
Presentation of AQUARIUS at Blue-Cloud 2026 General Assembly, during session "Synergies & Exploitation"	5/7/2024	Meetings	Research communities	50	Online
Presentation at 'Pint of Science' festival	13-15/05/2024	Other	Citizens	50	Galway, Ireland
Presentation at EMRA'24 (Workshop on EU-funded Marine Robotics and Applications)	27-29/05/2024	Conferences	Research communities	86	Arenzano, Italy
Proceedings of the 8th IAHR Europe Congress, Lisbon – Portugal, 4-7 June 2024	4-7/06/2024	Conferences	Research communities		Lisbon, Portugal
Poster at International Underwater Glider Conference (IUGC)	10-14/06/2024	Conferences	Research communities		Gothenburg, Sweden
Presentation on AQUARIUS at the 26th European Research Vessel Operators (ERVO) meeting	11-13/06/2024	Conferences	EU institutions		Vigo, Spain
Presentation of AQUARIUS at JERICO-S3 Final General Assembly.	18-21/06/2024	Conferences	Research communities	50-60	Brest, France
EuroGO-SHIP Workshop on Marine Research infrastructures	27/06/2024	Clustering activities	Research communities		
Presentation at International Radiowave Oceanography Workshop (ROW) 2024	3-5/09/2024	Meetings	Research communities	100+	Plymouth, UK
Poster presentation at EU Polar Science Week	3-6/09/2024	Conferences	Research communities	300	Copenhagen, Denmark
AQUARIUS Brokerage event, as side event to the ICES Annual Science Conference	10/9/2024	Conferences	Research communities		Gateshead, United Kingdom
Second AQUARIUS brokerage event, at MonGOOS General Assembly & Workshop	1/10/2024	Meetings	Research communities		Malaga, Spain
Presentation at the 3as Jornadas Luso Espanolas de Hidrografia (3JLEH)	9-11/10/2024	Conferences	Research communities		Cadiz, Spain

Dissemination Activity name	Date	Type of Dissemination Activity	Who? Target audience reach	Audience Size	Location (city, country)
Presentation on AQUARIUS at EGI 2024		Conferences	Research communities		Lecce, Italy
Presentations at 11th FerryBox Workshop	1-2/10/2024	Meetings	Other	75	Helsinki, Finland
Presentation to ICES Ecosystem Observation Steering Group (EOSG)	2/10/2024	Meetings	Research communities	29	Online
Presentation to the ICES Scallop Assessment Working Group (WGScallop)	10/10/2024	Meetings	Research communities	44	Online
Presentation at the MarBlue 2024 Conference on MDM in AQUARIUS	24/10/2024	Conferences	Research communities	200	Constanta, Romania
Presented to the Explorer Education Program	10/17/2024	Meetings	Citizens	12	Online
Marblue Conference Observing the Black Sea session Presentation, Poster and exhibition area	23/10/2024	Conferences	Research communities	200	Constanta, Romania
AQUARIUS brokerage webinar	6/11/2024	Other	Other	81	Online
Presentation of AQUARIUS at the SLU Aqua research collegium	7/11/2024	Conferences	Research communities	63	Lysekil, Sweden
HYPERSPECTRAL 2024	13-15/11/2024	Conferences	Research communities	190	Noordwijk, The Netherlands
FLIS airborne infrastructure, 3rd WORKSHOP ON INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN SPACEBORNE IMAGING SPECTROSCOPY	11-13/11/2024	Conferences	Research communities	300	ESA-ESTEC, Netherlands
Pull-up-banner at the final conference on Project Marine Management and Climate (Nordic Council)	13/11/2024	Conferences	Research communities	150	Göteborg, Sweden
Poster and presentation about AQUARIUS at the Swedish Marine Research Days 2024	26-28/11/2024	Conference	Research communities	90	Kalmar. Sweden
Tour of SLU's research vessel R/V Svea for participants at the Swedish Marine Research Days 2024	27/11/2024	Other	Research communities	60	Kalmar Sweden
AQUARIUS Training Webinar	27/11/2024	Education and training events	Research communities	12	Online

Dissemination Activity name	Date	Type of Dissemination Activity	Who? Target audience reach	Audience Size	Location (city, country)
AQUARIUS Project and Call	02/12/24 & 4/12/24	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Research communities		Online
AQUARIUS Poster at the BS-SEOS Project meeting	17/12/2024	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Research communities	25	
Presentation of the AQUARIUS to the French Regional & Offshore scientific commissions	04/12/2024 & 06/12/2024	Meetings	Research communities	50	Paris, France
Poster including Aquarius Project at IMDIS Conference (Marine Data and Information Systems)	27-29/05/2024	Conferences	Research communities	50	Bergen, Norway
Poster Presentation at the Mission Ocean and Waters Forum	4th-6th March 2025	Clustering activities	Research communities		
AQUARIUS poster at VLIZ Marine Science Day	5/3/2025	Conferences	Research communities	300-500	Brugge, Belgium
FLIS – Flying Laboratory of Imaging Systems for environmental research; data acquisition and processing, EUFAR webinar- The European landscape of airborne infrastructure and future	28/03/2025	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	30	
AQUARIUS Booth, poster and oral presentation at EGU 2025 (Check did MARIS present)	27 April - 2 May 2025	Conferences	Research communities		Vienna, Austria
Promotion of TA call 2 at Ocean ICU General Assembly	19-23/05/2025	Project General Assembly	Research community	60	Sopot, Poland
AQUARIUS at shared booth at European Maritime Day 2025	21-23/05/2025	Conferences	Other		Cork, Ireland
Promotion of TA Call 2 and dissemination of material at OceanICU Annual Meeting	23/05/2025	Conferences	Research communities	90	Sopot, Poland
Presented 'Spaceborne, airborne and drone-based water quality monitoring' and AQUARIUS TA call 2 at EUFAR Webinar: 25 years of airborne research in Europe	06/04/2025	Meetings	Research communities	40	Online
Recent upgrades of Flying Laboratory of Imaging Systems (FLIS), 44th EARSeL Symposium	25-29/05/2025	Conferences	Research communities	300	Prague, Czech Republic
AQUARIUS Presentation at the 27th European Research Vessel Operators (ERVO) annual meeting	06/03/2025	Meetings	Research communities		

Dissemination Activity name	Date	Type of Dissemination Activity	Who? Target audience reach	Audience Size	Location (city, country)
Demo, to present AQUARIUS Funding Call for Access and Remote Sensing Infrastructure offered by VITO, presented at VITO booth at the ESA Living Planet Symposium	24/06/2025	Conferences	Research communities	10000	Vienna, Austria
Online poster Oceans Conference Brest; Onsite dissemination of TA Call 2 material	16-19/06/2025	Conferences	Research communities	500	Brest, France
AQUARIUS-EMSO poster focused on access to deep-sea infrastructures at One Ocean Science Conference	3-5/06/2025	Conferences		800	France
Dissemination of Call 2 promotional material at ICES Annual Science Conference	17/09/2025	Conferences	Research communities	150	Lithuania
Presented a Poster and disseminated Call 2 promotional materials at EU Mission Ocean Presidency Conference	23-24/09/2025	Conferences	Research communities	350	Nyborg, Denmark
Poster and booth at All-Atlantic Forum 2025	25-26/09/2025	Conferences	Research communities	150+	Brussels, Belgium
Presentation at International Ship Operators Meeting (IRSO)	23/09/2025	Conferences	Research communities	130	Bergen, Norway
Blue Cloud 2026 Workshop	06/11/2026	Clustering activities	Research communities	100	Brussels, Belgium
Atlantic Days Galway, including the Interreg Atlantic Area Programme Annual Event, the Blue Synergies Event, and the 12th Atlantic Stakeholders Platform Conference (ASPC 2025).	12/11/2025-13/11/2025	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Research communities	70	Galway, Ireland
EMODnet and Marine Research Infrastructures workshop	26/11/2025	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	70	Brussels, Belgium
AQUARIUS material disseminated at EMODnet and Digital Ocean Forum	27/11/2025	Conferences	Research communities	270	Brussels, Belgium
AQUARIUS Pull-up banner displayed at EU Information Day– Horizon Europe Work Programmes 2026–2027: Marine and Maritime Related Topics	12/10/2025	Meetings	Research communities	50-70	Galway, Ireland

Appendix 2 Overview of outreach and engagement campaigns for TA Calls

Overview of outreach and engagement campaign for TA Call 1

Year	2024					2025
Month	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan
Campaign	Campaign 1: Introducing RI Catalogue		Campaign 2: Introducing Call 1	Campaign 3: Countdown to the call	Campaign 4: Open Call	
Deliverables, Milestones, Tasks	D 3.1 (June 2024): AQUARIUS Call Priority; D 6.1 (July 2024): AQUARIUS Data Gaps; D7.1(August 2024) Communication and Dissemination Plan; D				D1.2 (November 2024)AQUARIUS Brokerage Events; D5.1 (November 2024) Database of Research Infrastructure User	D5.2 (January 2025) Training on use of AQUARIUS Access Platform
Toolkits	AQUARIUS Communication and Outreach Toolkit		AQUARIUS Funding Call 1 Toolkit for partners			
Newsletters * Newsflash			AQUARIUS Newsletter 1	Newsflash - AQUARIUS Funding Call 1 now open		
Press release				Press release Issued		
Email campaigns			Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers
Blogs		Frank Armstrong (MI) Blog with focus on AQUARIUS RI Catalogue				
Videos		Frank Blog Video		AQUARIUS Promo Video; Insights for applicants with Anneli Strobel Video		
Website			Website updated with all relevant information for Call2	Link to Transnational Access Platform now live		
News (Monthly)	Identifying priorities for AQUARIUS Transnational Access Funding Calls; Identifying relevant Data	The first AQUARIUS Brokerage Event Highlights Transnational Access	AQUARIUS at the MonGOOS General Assembly; Maximising the value of data	First Transnational Access Funding Call Open; Join our AQUARIUS Webinar and AQUARIUS Webinar - Call 1 Announcement and how to apply	Inside the First AQUARIUS Webinar; Link to webinar and training on	First AQUARIUS Regional Lighthouse Access Call is
Webinars				AQUARIUS Training Webinar		
Social Media W1	Countdown to RI Catalogue launch	1st AQUARIUS brokerage event announcement; ICES Annual Science Conference	MonGOOS GA: 2nd AQUARIUS Brokerage Event		Learn how to submit your proposal in the AQUARIUS TA Platform	Open funding call! Apply by 20 January
		Frank Armstrong blog with focus on RI catalogue	Photos and recap from 2nd AQUARIUS Brokerage event	AQUARIUS Webinar Announcement: Learn about the Funding Call	FAQs about AQUARIUS Call 1	
Social Media W2	Call priority report by Finish Environment Institute	Happening today: 1st AQUARIUS Brokerage Event		AQUARIUS Video: 1 to go until the Launch of the 1st AQUARIUS Funding Call	FAQs about AQUARIUS Call 1	Make sure to register your application early
	Three weeks until the launch of the AQUARIUS RI Catalogue	Join the AQUARIUS Brokerage event	AQUARIUS Webinar Announcement: Learn about the Funding Call - Register	Join the AQUARIUS Webinar Today!	FAQs about AQUARIUS Call 1	
		Photos and Recap: 1st AQUARIUS Brokerage Event		Webinar recording is now available		

Overview of outreach and engagement campaign for TA Call 1 (continued)

Year	2024					2025
Month	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan
Campaign	Campaign 1: Introducing RI Catalogue	Campaign 2: Introducing Call 1	Campaign 3: Countdown to the call	Campaign 4: Open Call		
Social Media W3	Data Gaps Report	New article: Summary of 1st AQUARIUS Brokerage event	4 weeks until the launch of the 1st AQUARIUS TA Call + RI catalogue tour	The 1st AQUARIUS Funding Call is now open! + AQUARIUS promo video	Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures in all EU Mission Ocean & Waters Lighthouse Regions	Only 5 days left to apply
	AQUARIUS in Numbers - 2 weeks to go to catalogue launch		SeaTechWeek	AQUARIUS at Hyperspectral 2024	FAQs about AQUARIUS Call 1	The deadline to apply is approaching
Social Media W4	RV Celtic Explorer feature	New AQUARIUS Gallery	Register to AQUARIUS Webinar on Call 1	AQUARIUS Training Webinar Announcement		The deadline to apply is today
	Meet the AQUARIUS RI providers - 1 week to go until catalogue launch		European Open Science Symposium and AQUARIUS Open Data	Ocean Knowledge Conference 2024 - Funding opportunity for marine and Freshwater Researchers: AQUARIUS Call 1		The first AQUARIUS Funding Call is officially closed
Social Media W5	Its Launch Day! AQUARIUS RI Catalogue is live		AQUARIUS 3rd Brokerage Event Announcement: MarBlue Conference	Insights for applicants with Anneli Strobel		
			AQUARIUS Newsletter 1	Register for the AQUARIUS Training Webinar		
			Join the AQUARIUS Webinar	Euro-Bioimaging Webinar		
				Join us tomorrow the Training Webinar on the Transnational Access Platform		
Events by AQUARIUS		ICES Science Conference: AQUARIUS Brokerage Event	MonGOOS GA: AQUARIUS Brokerage Event	Tour of SLU's research vessel R/V Svea for participants at the Swedish Marine Research Days 2024	AQUARIUS Brokerage webinar	
			MarBlue: AQUARIUS Brokerage Event	Poster & presentation about AQUARIUS at the Swedish Marine Research Days 2024	AQUARIUS Poster at the BS-SEOS Project meeting	
Events (Third Party)			Presentations at 11th FerryBox Workshop	Euro-Bioimaging Webinar: Info session on 1st AQUARIUS Call	Presentation at the 3as Jornadas Luso Espanolas de Hidrografia (3JLEH)	
			Presentation to ICES Ecosystem Observation Steering Group (EOSG)	Hyperspectral 2024	Presentation of the AQUARIUS to the French Regional & Offshore scientific commissions	
			Presented to the Explorer Education Program	Presentation of AQUARIUS at the SLU Aqua research collegium		
			Presentation to the ICES Scallop Assessment Working Group (WGSscallop)	Pull-up-banner at the final conference on Project Marine Management and Climate (Nordic Council)		

Overview of outreach and engagement campaign for TA Call 2

Year	2025						
Month	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct
Campaign	Campaign 1: Introducing the Call (name, dates, who can apply)		Campaign 2: RI deep dive (Advertising Infrastructures that were not chosen on Call 1)		Campaign 3: Countdown to the call	Campaign 4: Open Call	
Deliverables, Milestones, Tasks	D7.2: Exploitation Plan Outline template (MARIS) Due 30-April	M7. TA campaigns selected for funding Call1 (AWI) 31-May M18. Training Programme Developed (OGS) 31- May	M6. TA Projects initiated based on call 1(MI) 30-June D3.5. Call Documentation for the Transnational Access Call I (M8) and Call II (M15)		M14. Call 1 Logistical Evaluation Completed (RBINS) 31-july M15. AQUARIUS TA Schedule Created (MI) M26. Launch of promo campaigns for TA Calls 2 (SSBE) M34. Communications & Dissemination Plan 2.0 (SSBE) D4.2 Selection report from OEP for Call 1 M(18) and Call 2 (M36) (RBINS) D5.3 Technical Training Hub - Training Material Repository (OGS)		
Project activities and dependencies	TA call 1 evaluation ongoing.	Announcement of Funded Projects Circulate Comms Toolkit and all info to partners	Spotlight on available RI for Call 2: Depends on knowing RI but should be fine by this time				
Toolkits & press releases		Communication Toolkit for pre-launch circulated to partners mid-May			Press release circulated to partners + Updated Call 2 Toolkit		
Email campaigns	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers
Newsletters - Newsflash		Newsflash! Call opens Sept, but start preparing now.	Newsletter: CALL 2 Introduction & specificities	Newsflash - Updated Eligibility Criteria		Newsflash on 02 Sept: Call open! Who, what, why, how and when of Call 2	Newsletter Oct 1st: Focus on Call
Blogs		Blog with Carlos Barrera (RI and Training)		Blog with Bernadette Ni Chonghaile (Call 2 updates)		Blog with coordinator to promote TA Call 2	
Videos	Meet the partners - Dre Catrissa	Updated promo video (EMD) - Call 2	Meet the partners - Aodhan Fitzgerald (TA Call 2) Video			Anneli Strobel and Elisabeth de Maio	
Website	Website updates for TA Call 2: new banner; information on call; clearly available RI	Updates to TA Page	Updates on how to apply	Projects funded under TA Call1 (inspiration)			
News (Monthly)	AQUARIUS at EUFAR Webinar; Behind the scenes with of AQUARIUS with Adre Cattrijsse; Advancing science with citizen science;	AQUARIUS at EGU; AQUARIUS attends EMD; AQUARIUS at OceanICU GA	AQUARIUS Partner EMSO-ERIC showcases RI at one Ocean Science Congress; The EU Ocean Pact; AQUARIUS at Oceans 2025; AQUARIUS at ESA Living Planet Symposium; Meet the people behind AQUARIUS Aodhan Fitzgerald	Call for scientific experts - AQUARIUS pool of experts	Get ready for the 2nd AQUARIUS Funding Call for Access!	The 2nd AQUARIUS Funding Call for Access is now open; News item: Who, Why, What & How of TA, Call 2; Link to TAP goes live	Apply before the deadline+ how to apply

Overview of outreach and engagement campaign for TA Call 2 (continued)

Year	2025						
Month	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct
Campaign	Campaign 1: Introducing the Call (name, dates, who can apply)		Campaign 2: RI deep dive (Advertising Infrastructures that were not chosen on Call 1)		Campaign 3: Countdown to the call	Campaign 4: Open Call	
Webinars			WP6 data management webinar available on website			AQUARIUS Brokerage Webinar	
Social Media W1	RICH Webinar	AQUARIUS Year 1 Report	Apply for AQUARIUS Seabed Mapping Training programme	AQUARIUS FAIR data management resources		AQUARIUS 2nd Call now open!	Training Opportunities
	Blue Cloud Consultation	AQUARIUS EGU	Call 2 is on the Horizon	Important update for AQUARIUS Applicants: Eligibility		AQUARIUS Call opens tomorrow	TAP Webinar Reminder
					Updated Eligibility Criteria (Targeting Industry)	Funded projects kick-off	
Social Media W2	EUFAR Webinar	Revamped AQUARIUS Video	EU Ocean Pact at UNOC	AQUARIUS RIs for the Mediterranean		TAP Webinar - TAP video	TAP Webinar Reminder
	PLOCAN Summer School Training	ECR - Opportunities - Seabed Mapping	Deadline for applying to PLOCAN Glider School		1 month to go until Call 2 opens!	Spotlight on our Mobile Marine Observation Platforms	Call for Experts
			INFOMAR Seabed Mapping Training - Applications Closed			TAP Webinar - TAP video	Funded projects - post
Social Media W3	Dre Video	Video Carlos Barreras - PLOCAN Summer School	Aodhan Video promoting call 2	Call for experts - AQUARIUS pool of experts	AQUARIUS Funded Projects	Spotlight on Fixed Marine Facilities	Webinar Recording - How to apply FAQs
	EGU	AQUARIUS at EMD	AQUARIUS at Oceans 2025		3 Weeks to go until Call 2 Opens!	Targeted post for Citizen Science	2 Weeks to go! Don't wait to the last minute to apply
					AQUARIUS Training hub post	Targeted post for industry	INFOMAR Seabed Mapping
Social Media W4	Citizen Science Month - Call 2	Get Ready for the 2nd AQUARIUS Funding Call	Countdown to the 2nd AQUARIUS Funding Call	Bernie Blog - Focus on 2nd Call	2 Weeks to go	ALL-ATLANTIC Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance Forum 2025	1 Week to go! How to apply?
					News article: Get ready to apply to the Second AQUARIUS Funding Call	TAP Webinar - TAP video	FAQ Section on website
Social Media W5	AQUARIUS at EGU	Presenting the AQUARIUS Funding Call at OceanICU GA	AQUARIUS at the ESA Living Planet Symposium 2025	AQUARIUS RIs for the Baltic and North Sea	1 Week to go until Call 2 Opens!	TAP Webinar Reminder	The deadline for applications is approaching! Make sure you wont miss it.
	PLOCAN Summer School Training				AQUARIUS Funded Projects		
	Launching AQUARIUS Call 2 at EGU (3 pnsts)						